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EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL PROGRAMS RESULTS WITHIN THE NETWORK PARADIGM

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Annotation: A systematic analysis of domestic and foreign experience in assessing the scientific and technical programs results has been carried out. The possibilities and limitations of the directions for assessing the relevance of scientific research and development are revealed: an examination designed to reduce the influence of subjectivity on the final assessment, and scientometrics as a way to generalize the opinions of specialists about the published scientific results. It is noted that effective diffusion and management of the scientific and technical programs results is achieved within the network paradigm. Scientific and methodological approaches to the actors classification in the process of scientific and technical programs results diffusion within the scientific cooperation framework among potential recipients of knowledge are proposed.

Keywords: scientific and technical program, demand for scientific results, system analysis, scientific collaboration, network paradigm

ЭФФЕКТИВНОЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ РЕЗУЛЬТАТАМИ НАУЧНО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ПРОГРАММ В СЕТЕВОЙ ПАРАДИГМЕ

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Аннотация: Проведен систематический анализ отечественного и зарубежного опыта оценки результатов научно-технических программ. Выявлены возможности и ограничения направлений оценки актуальности научных исследований и разработок: экспертиза, призванная снизить влияние субъективности на итоговую оценку, и наукометрия как способ обобщения мнения специалистов об опубликованных научных результатах. Отмечается, что эффективное распространение и управление результатами научно-технических программ достигается в рамках сетевой парадигмы. Предложены научно-методические подходы к классификации акторов в процессе распространения результатов научно-технических программ в рамках научного сотрудничества между потенциальными реципиентами знаний.

Ключевые слова: научно-техническая программа, востребованность научных результатов, системный анализ, научное сотрудничество, сетевая парадигма

Innovation is a resource-intensive process, and the fewer resources are allocated for innovation within the framework of national innovation systems (NIS), the lower the innovative activity of its actors. The strongest results should be supported, allowing the production of products with high added value that can compete not only on the national market, but also on foreign markets. NIS actors are interested in the most rational use of available resources and the use of modern mechanisms and tools for the scientific and technical programs results implementation. It is important to take into account all the key characteristics of scientific results.

Fundamentally, a systematic analysis of scientific developments should include particular assessment tasks in such aspects as relevance and feasibility, which should be consolidated into a single criterion model, the use of which, in combination with methods and analysis algorithms, will allow obtaining generalized characteristics of the scientific and technical programs results effectiveness, determine the possibilities of reduction paths from the formulation of scientific tasks to the practical implementation of the results obtained [1-3]. The research and development carried out should not be limited only to the participants of federal target programs, the participation of private business, small and medium-sized innovative companies is necessary.

Scientific knowledge plays a vital role in economic growth, which is generally recognized by experts in endogenous growth [4-6]. The strength of knowledge depends on whether it spreads, as well as on the depth and breadth of distribution, of course in addition to the very value of knowledge. As knowledge is disseminated, the information and experience gained by both parties will increase linearly; if knowledge continues to be disseminated with constant feedback and expansion of the problems under consideration, new information will increase exponentially. The modern knowledge society is characterized by the rapid growth of knowledge-based communities specializing in the production and reproduction of knowledge, the acquisition and exchange of knowledge, and the use of information technology. The production and creation of scientific knowledge does not depend on a particular actor; instead, knowledge is disseminated, exchanged and circulated between different organizations. The real and potential competitiveness of actors is embodied in the acquisition and mastery of scientific knowledge and innovative potential. Effective dissemination of knowledge can enhance its competitiveness and value, as well as its optimal use in practice. The dissemination of scientific knowledge is the link between the acquisition of knowledge and its application. Effective dissemination and management of knowledge is achieved within a networked paradigm.

Much effort has been made by academics to improve understanding of knowledge dissemination across various networks. In accordance with the strength of connection between network members [7], a theory of weak ties of social networks has been proposed, emphasizing the importance of "connection" between network members in the knowledge and information dissemination. In [8, 9], a comparison was made of the distribution of knowledge in regular, random networks and networks of the "small world" (such networks have a high value of the clustering coefficient and a low value of the average path length between nodes) and it was found that the network of the "small world" is the most an effective structure for the dissemination of knowledge. In [10, 11], it is argued that a scale-free structure is more effective for the knowledge dissemination.

The processes of collective production and dissemination of knowledge for the science and technology development have attracted the attention of sociologists who study the knowledge dissemination in a historical context [12, 13]. In the context of the research growing complexity, collaboration is one of the most important factors in the new scientific research knowledge dissemination in the scientific community. The scientific cooperation process is accompanied by the dissemination, sharing and exchange of both explicit and implicit knowledge between research organizations [14].

A scientific collaboration network, especially a co-authorship network consciously formed by scientists, is a structured form of knowledge sharing. The self-organizing nature of scientific creativity in the scientific and technological progress knowledge creation and dissemination determines that the scientific cooperation network is the most appropriate way to transfer and disseminate scientific knowledge.

In the process of scientific cooperation, the scientific and technological progress results exchange and dissemination can occur through social links between research organizations, including individual scientists, institutions, regions, countries, etc. From the point of view of information theory, the knowledge dissemination consists of four elements: information, source of information, channel and information receiver.

Modeling the knowledge dissemination in scientific collaboration networks can help visualize the knowledge dissemination through scientific collaboration, identify the dynamic mechanism for the knowledge dissemination in scientific collaboration networks, and better manage and regulate the knowledge dissemination generated by scientific and technical programs.

Studies of the evolution mechanisms and the knowledge dissemination dynamics patterns are carried out using various mathematical models, the number of which is relatively small, but most of the studies are of a qualitative nature.

Well-known models from disciplines such as complex systems theory and sociology are commonly used. The knowledge dissemination process is accompanied by the creation and development of a knowledge dissemination network, and to build a knowledge dissemination model, a tangible or intangible knowledge dissemination carrier network is required. Currently, most academics consider co-authorship and citation [15] as ways to disseminate knowledge and explore abstract ideas about the disseminating knowledge process [16].

A retrospective analysis of the scientific and technical activity essence allows to note that before scientific activity acquired a "mass" character, the dissemination of scientific results, the assessment of scientific results and the actors of scientific activity were a matter of personal or (more often) written contacts of individual scientists. The creation of scientifically based models for assessing the scientific and technical potential and determining the programs

scientific and technical development directions began to be recognized as a scientific problem when involving a significant part of the society intellectual and material resources in the activity of obtaining scientific knowledge, its dissemination and practical application. The specificity of assessment sets its own requirements for the specified model, predetermining its multi-criteria nature and the limited availability of information.

Currently, two fundamental scientific directions for the development of models for assessing the modern scientific and technical programs results relevance have been formed: models for aggregating expert opinions, designed to reduce the influence of subjectivity on the final assessment, and scientometrics as a way to generalize the specialists opinions about published scientific results. Thus, two approaches are used: expert and formal. When using the expert approach, a problem arises due to a certain influence of the subjective factor on the expert opinion final conclusions. First, experts, as scientists, belong to different scientific schools, and, therefore, adhere to a certain point of view on the certain scientific problems solution. Secondly, experts are specialists in certain areas of research and, since the body of experts is finite, then, as a rule, the aggregate range of scientific interests of experts turns out to be much narrower than the research thematic areas range. And, finally, thirdly, the principle of forming a corps of experts should be focused on the most authoritative scientists representation in the domestic and world scientific community. However, when forming the body of experts, as a rule, the principle of recommendations by various organizations is used, which already carries the interest conflicts risks.

The methodological basis of the formal (quantitative) approach is the system of bibliometric indicators. The initial data for calculating these indicators actually reflect the attitude of the world scientific community to the research results of a particular scientist, team, research organization and educational institution presented in publications. Thus, in this case, the expert is actually the entire world scientific community. And as a result, there are no problems with the influence of subjective factors that occur with a qualitative expert approach.

However, it should be noted that, from a methodological point of view, the practice of using these data is far from always correct. In particular, the problems associated with insufficient identification of scientific activity subjects, with the dependence of the publications citation level on the research process organization characteristics, publication activity, the scientists distribution in various thematic areas and, last but not least, the influence of practice and ethics are not taken into account citations in a particular scientific direction.

For example, even in the most authoritative university ranking systems, when using such bibliometric indicators as the total number of publications, the citations number, the difference in the research thematic spectrum carried out in different universities is not taken into account.

When using formal methods to assess the scientific activity subjects research level and scope, data on the articles citation level and publications impact factor values are usually used [17]. It is known that the procedure for organizing research, the tradition of presenting their results, as well as the number of scientists differ significantly in different areas and fields of science. Without taking into account these factors, it is impossible to obtain reliable data to describe various aspects of development in specific areas of fundamental science: characteristics of publication activity, the demand for research results by the world scientific community, the role of various types of publications (research articles, conference proceedings, reviews, monographs), bibliometric characteristics of publications, the publications national volumes contribution scale and quality to the global flow in specific areas. Unfortunately, in most cases these indicators are used without taking into account the publications studied massifs thematic structure peculiarities [18].

In recent years, the scientific community and decision-makers in the field of science management have become aware of the shortcomings of these scientific areas in creating models for assessing scientific and technical potential and determining the state programs scientific and technical development directions. Numerous works are devoted to the criticism of methods for aggregating expert opinions and identifying the shortcomings of scientometric indices as methods of objectively assessing the scientific and technical potential and determining the scientific and technological development directions [19, 20].

The claims are related to the lack of direct links between scientometric indicators and the quality and significance of scientific results, with discrepancies between expert assessments and scientometric data, and inconsistency of the expert assessments themselves. The fundamental limitation of the adequate use of scientometric indicators as target variables characterizing scientific activity is indicated by the well-known Goodhart's law in economics. Goodhart's law states that when an economic indicator becomes a target for economic policy, the previous empirical laws using this indicator cease to apply. Thus, any observed statistical pattern is prone to destruction as soon as it is under pressure to control it. A common place was the indication of the need to use various formal approaches to assess the scientific and technical potential and determine the scientific and technological development directions. Moreover, scientometric indicators exist only for already published texts and do not help to assess the results of unpublished and promising scientific research projects.

Despite the shortcomings widely known to the professional community, at present, scientometric data are decisive for the attitude of society to scientific activity, as well as for political decisions and financial support of science. It should be noted that in recent decades, with significant changes in the social conditions for the functioning and funding of science, the methodology of scientometrics has not

practically changed, and scientometrics itself has turned into international business, influencing (including, in its own interests) on the development of science and on the activities of related with the science of state and public institutions. The formation, in addition to scientometric data and expert assessments, of content-oriented characteristics determined on the basis of quantitative and qualitative models for assessing scientific and technical potential and determining the scientific and technical development directions has high scientific, practical and social significance.

It is advisable to present the scientific and technical programs results disseminating process in more detail than in existing formal approaches, dividing the actors into separate classes: the class of susceptibility, the interested class, the carrier class, the skeptical class and the antagonistic class. In the initial period of knowledge dissemination, most of the actors will belong to the receptive class, with several actors in the interested class – who got acquainted with the new knowledge of scientific and technical program, but did not disseminate it and a small number of actors are knowledge carriers. In addition, there may be competing and mutually exclusive ideas (for example, when susceptible actors reject the idea and become skeptics represented by the antagonistic class). Moreover, actors may become immune and not take an interest in new knowledge. Different actors can choose classes based on their scientific and technical interests.

On the basis of the described scheme, it is proposed to classify actors in the scientific and technical programs results disseminating process in the scientific cooperation framework among knowledge potential recipients. NIS actors can move from one class to another with a certain probability. The rules for the evolution of knowledge dissemination in scientific collaboration networks are then applied. In addition, a knowledge dissemination model is formed based on the differential dynamics methodology. A detailed analysis of the relationship between the distributions of degrees (number of links) of nodes in the network and the evolution of knowledge dissemination is carried out in order to identify effective ways of scientific and technical programs results disseminating in scientific cooperation networks. Finally, an empirical analysis of the knowledge dissemination in institutional scientific cooperation networks within the framework of a specific scientific and technical program is carried out.

Planning, receipt, publication and promotion of the state programs scientific research results occur in conditions of incomplete information. Researchers, experts and decision-makers in the scientific policy field and scientific research organization do not have comprehensive information about the planned and ongoing research, about the results obtained. This is due not only to delays between the receipt of scientific results and their publication, insufficient completeness and correctness of the search results for scientific information, the lack of a direct connection between scientometric indicators and the scientific

results quality, but also by the presence of unpublished or published results in poorly accessible editions, often closed research plans, language barriers, finally, limited human abilities to receive and comprehend information. The same reasons make it insufficiently reliable to predict possible directions for successful research and identify the so-called breakthrough scientific directions on the basis of expert and scientometric analysis of the scientific and technological progress results. The proposed scientific and methodological approaches to assessing the modern scientific and technical programs results relevance in the framework of scientific cooperation among potential recipients of knowledge will help determine the possibilities of shortening the path from the formulation of scientific problems to the practical implementation of the results obtained. Taking into account heterogeneous information in assessing the quality of scientific results and actors of scientific activity contributes to an increase in the adequacy of responses to the great challenges posed within the scientific and technical programs framework.

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